

Surface Tension of Sodium and Potassium Amalgams at the Amalgam-Benzene Interface.

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A systematic study of sodium amalgams containing high percentages of sodium was made by Vanstone who by varying the proportion of sodium and mercury and studying the mixture with respect to thermal diagram (Trans. Faraday Soc., 1911, 7, 42) and electrical conductivity (Trans. Faraday Soc., 1914, 9, 291) found out the exact composition which corresponded to the formation of a definite compound.

Comparatively very little is known about the state of sodium-mercury and potassium-mercury mixtures in the liquid state, when only very small quantities of sodium and potassium are present in the mixtures.

Whilst the solid crystalline amalgams of the alkali and alkaline earth metals are regarded as definite chemical compounds, the corresponding liquid amalgams on the other hand have generally been regarded as mercurial solutions of this metal in the monatomic condition. George McP. Smith (Amer. Chem. J., 1907, 37, 506) does not agree with the latter view and has submitted evidence to show that even in the liquid state chemical compound formation takes place and the liquid amalgam constitutes solution of those salts in mercury. Vanstone (Jour. Chem. Soc., 1914, 105, 2617) and Maey (Zeit. Phy. Chem., 1899, 29, 119) have shown that the specific volume in

amalgams does not suffer any profound change when combination takes place between the metal sodium and mercury.

It was, therefore, considered desirable to examine such other physical properties, as surface tension, viscosity, etc., of amalgams in order to see if evidence could be accumulated for the views put forward by George McP. Smith (*loc. cit.*). These properties have been shown by Padoa 'Atti. R. Accad. Lincei, 1914, (V), 23, i, 88—94], Beck (Zeit. Phys. Chem., 1904, 48, 670) and others to undergo marked deviation from the mixture law when compound formation takes place and can be used with advantage to bring to light the behaviour of the mixtures at various concentrations.

The present investigation deals with the determination of the surface tension of sodium and potassium amalgams at the amalgam-benzene interface. To observe the various stages that amalgams undergo on change of concentration, the composition of amalgams has been varied by very small amounts of sodium and potassium.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Preparation of the Amalgam.

The amalgams were prepared by the electrolytic method of T. W. Richards (J. Amer. Chem. Soc., 1922, 44, 601). An electric current of about $4\frac{1}{2}$ amperes was passed through a saturated solution of Merck's pure sodium or potassium carbonate contained in a cell consisting of mercury cathode and an anode of platinum foil for a known interval of time. After passing the current for the required time, the electrodes were removed and the supernatant liquid was quickly poured out. The amalgam was then taken out in a beaker and was thoroughly washed 4 or 5 times with distilled water. Subsequently it was

taken in a separating funnel and after smart agitations, it was transferred to a vessel containing alcohol. The amalgam, after being washed over twice with alcohol to remove traces of water, was transferred to a flask which was evacuated and was heated for some minutes. Having thus dried the amalgam, it was well shaken in the flask and allowed to cool. When cooled, it was transferred to the storing vessel where it was kept out of contact with air. The amalgams of various concentrations were prepared by passing the same current under the same circumstances for varying intervals of time. In this way the sodium amalgams containing 0.033 % to 0.312 % of sodium and potassium amalgams containing 0.056 % to 0.182 % of potassium were prepared.

Storing of the Amalgam.

The amalgam was stored in a vessel A by an arrangement shown in figure 1. The vessel is set in connection with a large reservoir B of nitrogen through a U-tube C containing calcium chloride and a bottle D containing strong sulphuric acid. The amalgam was quickly poured out of the evacuated flask into the vessel A which was soon after fitted with an air-tight rubber stopper. The taps, 1, 2, 3 and 4 were opened and current of dry nitrogen was passed until the whole system was filled with it (nitrogen). As will be shown later, the amalgams, when kept as above, maintained their composition as such for a period of more than a fortnight.

Analysis of the Amalgams.

After rejecting 8 or 10 drops from the storage vessel, about 10 grams of the amalgam were taken in previously weighed weighing-bottles which were reweighed. The amalgam from the weighing-bottles was transferred to flasks to which a small quantity of water was added and

which were kept unexposed to air. The action of water on amalgam appeared to be very vigorous at first but slowed down after a short time. The reaction was allowed to proceed until no evolution of the gas could be noticed even on brisk shaking. The alkali (sodium or potassium hydroxide) formed in the reaction was titrated with standard hydrochloric acid which was prepared nearly of the same strength as the alkali solution.

At first some experiments were performed to see whether the composition of the amalgam remained the same on keeping it for some time in the storing vessel. The results of the above investigation are shown in the following table :—

TABLE I.

Time of standing of the amalgam.	Amount of Na. in 100 grams of the amalgam.	No. of estimations.
Immediately after storing ...	0.553 grams.	2
1 day ...	0.554 „	2
2 days ...	0.554 „	4
14 days ...	0.553 „	2
16 days ...	0.553 „	2

It will be seen from the above table that the strength of the amalgam remains constant for all intents and purposes.

By taking fractions of the amalgam from the various parts of the storing vessel, it was also observed that the composition was the same throughout. The above results indicate that the amalgam prepared as above is uniform in composition and does not change by keeping in an atmosphere of an inactive gas like nitrogen.

FIG 3

Measurement of the Interfacial Tension.

The interfacial tension between the liquid amalgam and pure benzene was measured by means of a modified form of Donnan's drop-pipette (*Zeit Phys. Chem.*, 1899, 31, 42) used by Bhatnagar and Garner (*Journ. Soc. Chem. Ind.*, 1920, 39, No. 13, 185T). The drop-pipette was kept at a constant temperature of 30° C by enclosing the whole apparatus in an incubator. The dropping-tube was so constricted nearly in the middle that a drop of the liquid amalgam took about 15 seconds to fall. The tip of the dropping-tube was made smooth by grinding it very carefully over a razor-hone and was always kept protected from foreign matter. The amalgam was filled in the bulb by means of capillary filters through the side tube up to a definite mark and was kept protected from air exposure by a small quantity of benzene just sufficient to cover the surface. It was found that benzene does not react appreciably with the amalgam. All necessary precautions were taken to prevent the entrance of dust in the apparatus.

It was shown by Lord Rayleigh [*Phil. Mag.*, 1899, (5), 48, 321] that the surface tension of a liquid can be determined by noting the weight of a drop falling from an orifice of a known diameter. Since then the method has been extended to the measurement of the surface tensions between liquid-liquid surface and liquid-gas surface.

This method has also been extended to the measurement of relative tensions of solutions of different concentrations. By counting the number of drops in a given volume of a liquid A, whose surface tension is required and a liquid B which is being used for comparison, the relative surface tension of A to B can be calculated from the following relation :—

$$\frac{T_1}{T_2} = \frac{n_2 d_1}{n_1 d_2} \quad \dots (1)$$

where T_1 , d_1 and n_1 are respectively the surface tension, the density and the number of drops of the liquid A in a volume V , and T_2 , d_2 and n_2 are the corresponding quantities for the comparing liquid B.

The tip of the dropping-tube was dipped in benzene contained in a small beaker and the number of drops of the amalgam, n_1 , and the mercury, n_2 , in a given volume were counted. For the sake of greater accuracy, the initial and final coincidence of the level of the liquids in the drop-pipette with the marks were observed through a high-power microscope.

Density of the Amalgam.

The density of the amalgam was measured in benzene by means of a specific gravity bottle. The densities of the amalgams with respect to water were calculated from the density of the benzene which was determined before hand. The values of densities thus obtained are in fair agreement with the values calculated from the specific volume and weights of Maey and Vanstone. The slight deviations which are observable are certainly due to the antiquated and unsatisfactory method used by Maey and Vanstone in preparing these amalgams.

Thus knowing the densities the relative interfacial tensions were calculated from the formula 1.

In the present investigation mercury has been used as a comparing liquid. The values for the interfacial tension of the liquid amalgams have been calculated from the above relative values by assuming the interfacial tension of mercury-benzene to be 100 dynes per cm.

The effect of the increasing quantity of sodium and potassium on the interfacial tension has been brought out in the following tables :—

TABLE II.

Interfacial Tension of Sodium Amalgam at 30°C.

Quantity of Na in 100 gms. of Amalgam.	Drop No.	Density.	$\frac{T_1}{T_2}$	I. T. in dynes per cm.
0.000 gms.	359	13.52	1.00	100
0.033 "	361	13.49	0.99	99
0.053 "	366	13.47	0.98	98
0.072 "	287	13.46	1.24	124
0.084 "	299	13.45	1.19	119
0.143 "	334	13.40	1.06	106
0.172 "	356	13.38	1.00	100
0.207 "	384	13.35	0.92	92
0.238 "	400	13.31	0.88	88
0.266 "	403	13.29	0.87	87
0.299 "	382	13.27	1.06	106
0.302 "	342	13.26	1.03	103
0.312 "	384	13.25	0.92	92

TABLE III.

Interfacial Tension of Potassium Amalgam at 30°C.

Quantity of K in 100 gms. of Amalgam.	Drop No.	Density.	$\frac{T_1}{T_2}$	I. T. in dynes per cm.
0.000 gms.	369	13.52	1.00	100
0.056 "	428	13.47	0.86	86
0.068 "	442	13.46	0.83	83
0.101 "	416	13.43	0.88	88
0.126 "	422	13.41	0.87	87
0.156 "	432	13.39	0.85	85
0.171 "	390	13.37	0.94	94
0.182 "	400	13.36	0.91	91

Discussion of Results.

The results of the above investigation are shown in Tables II and III. The interfacial tension of eleven different sodium amalgams containing from 0.033 to

0.312 gms. per cent. of sodium, and of seven different potassium amalgams, containing from 0.056 to 0.182 gms. per cent. of potassium, has been measured. By plotting the interfacial tensions as abscissa against the concentrations of the alkali metals as ordinates, curves as shown in figures 2 and 3, are obtained.

It will be seen from the curves that the interfacial tension decreases as the concentration is increased from pure mercury to amalgams containing 0.06% of sodium and 0.08% of potassium. A discontinuity occurs at these concentrations which probably corresponds to the formation of compounds of sodium and potassium with mercury.

Again from C to D the interfacial tension decreases on further increasing the quantity of sodium or potassium until a second discontinuity is observed at D. This corresponds to the formation of another compound of sodium and potassium with mercury. The remaining portion of the curves also shows a similar behaviour from E to F.

Hine (J. Amer. Chem. Soc., 1917, 39, 882), while determining the electrical conductivities of sodium, potassium and lithium amalgams, also observed similar discontinuities in the case of sodium. The concentration of sodium in the amalgam at which the resistance begins to decrease almost corresponds to the point D on the curve (figure 2).

It will also be observed from the curves that the relation between the interfacial tension and concentration is linear at all concentrations excepting at points where discontinuity occurs. This is similar to the observations of Dorsey (Phil. Mag., 1897), Srebnitsky (J. Russ. Phys. Chem. Soc., 1912, 44, 145) and of others, namely, that the relation between the surface tension and concentration of solutions is a straight line.

The relation between the interfacial tension and concentration in this case can be expressed by

$$\sigma_A = \sigma(1 - kc)$$

where σ_A is the interfacial tension of the amalgam at the concentration C , σ has the value obtained by producing the curves to the abscissa and K is a constant, which is different for different parts of the curve.

This suggests that compounds of sodium and potassium with mercury are formed in the liquid state even at very low concentration of the alkali metal. At all other concentrations, the amalgam is probably a solution of the compounds and the metal in mercury.

To obtain further evidence of the conclusions already arrived at experiments for the determination of viscosity and other physical properties such as boiling point, etc., of these amalgams are in progress.

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